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O52: Improvement of a protocol for sanitation and early diagnostic validation of autochthonous grapevine germplasm

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INTRODUCTION

Early detection of infections in programs of production of virus-tested vine propagating material is of paramount importance to reduce costs of maintaining sanitized plants. In Apulia (Italy), the Regional Project “Re.Ge.Vi.P.”, aiming to the recovery, conservation and sanitary improvement of autochthonous vine cultivars, gave the cue to assess the minimum period of time required after sanitation to detect virus infections with molecular techniques.

Previous results of this work, relatively to the period 2013-2015, were given (Morelli et al., 2015) and regarded the analysis of the sanitary status of ca. 150 grape cultivars from which ca. 100 apexes were obtained by thermotherapy and *in vitro* culture. The work, continued in 2016-2017, allowed to confirm the previous findings which showed the good efficacy of the sanitation protocols and the reliability of applied diagnostic techniques in the whole process of production of vine propagating material.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The sanitary status of 43 autochthonous cultivars, collected in the 2016-2017 period, was assessed by ELISA on phloem tissues scraped from dormant cuttings.

According to the detected virus(es), each vine accession was submitted to specific sanitation protocols, already in use in our laboratory (Bottalico et al., 2003). These protocols consist in the application of *in vitro* culture of meristematic apexes when vines are infected by phloem-limited clostero and vitiviruses, and, limitedly to nepovirus infections, a preliminary thermotherapy treatment is also included.

After sanitation, three groups of 89, 60 and 49 plantlets, were submitted to qRT-PCR diagnostic assay (Faggioli et al., 2013), following, respectively, 70-100, 100-200 and more than 200 days the acclimatisation stage in the greenhouse. Molecular detection was repeated 5-6 months and again 2 years later, for those plantlets resulting virus-free at the first assessment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The initial sanitary status of the 43 accessions before sanitation is reported in Table 1.

Virus	GVA	GVB	GLRaV-1	GLRaV-2	GLRaV-3	GFLV	GFkV	ArMV
N. infected/tested accessions	22/43	1/43	10/43	4/43	28/43	16/43	22/43	0/43

Table 1. Sanitary status of the field collected vines

Comparison with the sanitary status of vine accessions recovered in 2013-2015 (Morelli et al., 2015) showed a similar virus distribution pattern characterized by the prevalence of *Grapevine leafroll-associated virus 3* (GLRaV-3), *Grapevine virus A* (GVA) and *Grapevine fleck virus* (GFkV).

After sanitation treatment, the qRT-PCR analysis showed that 62 out of 198 meristematic apices excised from 43 different cultivars were still infected, which corresponds to a 70% of successful sanitation process (Table 2).

Number of infected/tested apices							
GVA	GVB	GLRaV-1	GLRaV-2	GLRaV-3	GFLV	GFKV	ArMV
19/113	1/1	0/37	0/18	3/114	30/79	19/105	0/0

Table 2. Sanitary status of vines after sanitation

The lower efficiency of sanitation treatment on GFLV-infected vines was due to the failure of detecting this virus by ELISA before sanitation. Supposed lack of GFLV infection wrongly directed sanitation to be solely performed by *in vitro* culture of meristematic apices, thus skipping thermotherapy, which is indeed more efficient in eliminating nepoviruses.

Days after acclimatization	Number of infected/tested apices
70-100	34/89
100-200	20/60
>200	8/49

Table 3. Results of qPCR detection performed on apices, at different times following sanitation treatment

Comparison among the qRT-PCR results obtained at the three periods of assessment (Table 3) showed that as early as 70-100 days after acclimatisation, the assay is able to detect infected vines which escaped the sanitation, despite their young age and reduced size. Moreover, plantlets found virus-free at this first assay confirmed their status in the second and third assays, performed 5-6 months and 2-3 years later. A confidence interval sufficient to assess the sanitary status of sanitized vines requires performing ELISA for two vegetative seasons whereas the adoption of qRT-PCR provides consistent results on 3-months old greenhouse-transferred plantlets. These data show that qRT-PCR is an efficient tool for the early detection of grapevine viruses regulated by the Italian legislation, therefore allowing to dramatically reduce the number of sanitized vines to be maintained in the greenhouse, after their transfer from the growth chambers.

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